

Systematic Study of the Solvent Extraction of Metal-Tridentate Schiff Base Complexes

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GENERAL surveys of the solvent extraction of metals by oxine¹ (8-hydroxy quinoline), β -diketon² and N-benzoyl-N-phenyl hydroxylamine³ have been published. However, there has been no systematic study of solvent extraction of metals by Schiff base ligands. A general study of over twenty-five metal ions with salicylidene amino thiophenol has been carried out to assess the utility of this type of ligands in the solvent extraction. Schiff base ligands form strong complexes with several metals and as such are expected to be attractive as chelating ligands in extraction work.

Experimental

Reagents: All reagents used were of A. R. quality. Benzene (A.R.) was used as such without any further purification.

Preparation of 2-salicylidene amino thiophenol: The ligand was prepared by mixing *o*-amino thiophenol (Koch Light) and salicylaldehyde (England) in the ratio of 1 : 1 in benzene solution. The ligand separated out after 2 hr. It was filtered under suction. The ligand was recrystallised from benzene. Its melting point was found to be $135^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$.

Buffer solution: Perchloric acid, sodium perchlorate and sodium hydroxide mixtures were used as buffer between pH 2-4, acetic acid and ammonia mixtures for the pH range 4-8 and ammonium chloride ammonia mixtures for the pH range 8-10.

Instrumental measurements: Measurements of pH were made using Elico pH meter standardised with standard buffer solutions of pH 4 and 7. The accuracy of the instrument was ± 0.05 pH units. In every case, the pH of the aqueous phase was measured after the extraction. For spectrophotometric measurements, Bausch and Lomb spectrophotometer (Spectronic-20) was employed. The spectrophotometric measurements are reproducible to ± 0.01 absorbance unit. A calibration curve for each metal was obtained by using known concentrations of the metal and the unknown concentration of a metal was calculated from its respective calibration curve.

Procedure for solvent extraction: A solution of salicylidene amino thiophenol (10 ml of 1×10^{-2} M) in chloroform was added to an equal volume of an

aqueous phase containing the appropriate metal and buffer in a glass stoppered bottle and shaken in wrist type mechanical shaker. All experiments were carried out at $30 \pm 2^{\circ}$. The total ionic strength of the aqueous phase was kept constant at 0.1 M. The equilibration time was 3 hr unless otherwise specified. After the equilibrium had been reached, the two phases were separated and the concentration of the metal ion in the aqueous phase was determined spectrophotometrically. The distribution ratio (or per cent extraction) was then calculated from the known concentration of the metal, (1.0×10^{-4} M) and from the equilibration concentration of the metal in aqueous phase. The metal content in the organic phase was calculated by difference. The distribution ratio was calculated according to the following relationship:

$$D_o = \frac{\text{Total metal concentration in the organic phase}}{\text{Total metal concentration in the aqueous phase}}$$

Attainment of the extraction equilibrium: The rate of attainment of the equilibrium depends upon many factors. Primarily, it depends on the properties of the metal under investigation. Achievement of the equilibrium also depends on the pH and the concentration of the ligand. In general, it may be said that the rate of extraction increases with increasing pH values, irrespective of the ligand concentration. It is also observed that the rate of extraction increased with increase of equilibration time. Therefore, the equilibration time was kept at 3 hr for most of the metals unless otherwise specified.

All the metal extractions were carried out keeping the ligand concentration at 1×10^{-2} M and varying the pH of the aqueous phase from 2-10. The ligand dissolution took place at a pH higher than 10. Ishii has reported that nickel(II)⁴ and zinc(II)⁵ can be quantitatively extracted in the neutral or alkaline medium. It was thought worthwhile to carry out systematically the metal extraction studies at varying pH.

From the results obtained, the metals can be divided into the following three categories based on their extraction behaviour with salicylidene amino thiophenol:

- (A) Metals which are quantitatively extracted under certain pH ranges.
- (B) Metals with the maximum percentage extraction of 50% and above but less than 100%.
- (C) Metals with the maximum percentage extraction of less than 50%.

(A) **Metals which are quantitatively extracted under certain pH ranges:** The metals studied in this category are lead(II), cadmium(II), mercury(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), zinc(II), cerium(IV) and vanadium(V). All the above metals can be quantitatively extracted under proper conditions as shown in Fig. 1. Extraction of all these metals is sensitive to pH and rigorous control over pH is necessary for complete extraction.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Extraction curves for metal - salicylidene aminothiophenol

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Extraction curves for metal - salicylidene aminothiophenol

Lead(II): The extraction of lead(II) started from pH 6.0 and complete extraction took place from pH 8.0-8.5. The extraction decreased from pH 9.0 and above.

Cadmium(II): The extraction started from pH 5.0 and complete extraction took place between pH 7.0 and 10.0. Extraction and spectrophotometric determination of cadmium(II) seem to be attractive. Precipitation was observed at pH higher than 10.0.

Mercury(II) and vanadium(V): Both these metals were extracted completely from pH 3.5 to 8.5 and 1.0 to 4.5, respectively. The extraction of vanadium(V) decreased above pH 5.5.

Cerium(IV): The complete extraction took place between pH 2.0 and 4.0 and the extraction decreased above pH 4.0.

Cobalt(II), nickel(II) and zinc(II): Nickel(II) and zinc(II) can be extracted and estimated spectro-

photometrically as already reported⁶. Present studies also confirm the data reported in the literature. Cobalt(II) also can be extracted quantitatively in the pH range 5.5 to 7.3.

(B) *Metals with the maximum percentage extraction of 50% and above but less than 100%*: The metals in this category are calcium(II), lanthanum(III), aluminium(III), thorium(IV), zirconium(IV), uranium(VI), molybdenum(VI) and tungsten(VI).

The pH extraction curves are given in Figs. 2 and 3, from which it is clear that the metal extraction increases as the pH increased except in the case of molybdenum(VI) and tungsten(VI). Tungsten(VI) extraction decreased as the pH increased, perhaps due to the formation of polytungstic acids in the aqueous phase. In the extraction of molybdenum(VI), first the metal extraction decreased up to pH 2.0 and then increased as the pH increased. This behaviour may be due to the formation of different species of molybdenum at pH less than 2 when it exists essentially as H_2MO_4 according to Stary¹, and as some different species at pH above 2. In the case of calcium(II), thorium(IV) and aluminium(III), there was initial extraction but above certain pH values, there was slight precipitation. Therefore the extraction curves could not be plotted for the entire pH range.

(C) *Metals with the maximum percentage extraction of less than 50%*: The metals studied under this category are ferrous and ferric iron, manganese(II), beryllium(II) and chromium(III). The pH variation curves of these metals are shown in Fig. 4. Even when the equilibration time was prolonged to 12 hr in case of beryllium(II) and chromium(III), no significant extraction took place. In case of manganese(II), colour developed immediately which faded out in a few minutes. In case of iron(II) and iron(III), the spectrophotometric studies could not be performed at pH higher than 4.0 as there was precipitation.

Silver(I): Systematic studies of solvent extraction could not be carried out as the distribution ratios obtained by spectrophotometric methods were not reproducible due to absorption of silver ions on glass vessel. As there was no facility to determine the distribution ratios by radiometric method, the investigations are incomplete.

From the above study it can be seen that salicylidene amino thiophenol would be effective in the solvent extraction of various metals discussed above. Detailed investigations will be published subsequently.

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Detection and Chromatographic Separation of Phenols on Papers Impregnated with Ferric Hydroxide

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THE use of chromatographic papers loaded with Amberlite ion exchange resin has been reported by Clark¹. Scant attention has been paid on the chromatography of phenols on papers impregnated with inorganic ion exchangers. Use of papers impregnated with stannic molybdate, has been made in our laboratory for the separation of phenols².

Experimental

Preparation of ion exchange papers: Whatman No. 3 paper strips of size 14 × 3 cm were dipped in 0.1 M ferric nitrate solution for 15-20 sec and then dried at room temperature. These paper strips were then dipped in 0.1 M sodium hydroxide solution for 40-45 sec. The excess of reagent was drained off and the strips were dried at room temperature over the filter sheets. These treated strips were washed twice with demineralized water to remove the excess of reagent. Finally, the strips were dried again at room temperature and used as such for chromatography.

Procedure: One or two spots of test solution in ethanol were placed on the paper strip with the help of a glass capillary. The paper was conditioned for 15 min and then solvent was allowed to ascend 11 cm in every case using 20 × 5 cm glass jars.

Results and Discussion

Detection: The colours observed with the phenols are listed below:

β -Hydroxy benzoic acid, β -naphthol, vanilline, *p*-nitrophenol, *m*-cresol, *p*-cresol, *o*-nitrophenol, picric acid, phloroglucinol, 4-(4-nitrophenyl)-azo resorcinol, di-(2-hydroxyphenylimino) ethane, 4-chlorophenol and 4-(2-pyridilazo) resorcinol gave yellow spots.

Tannic acid, α -naphthol, pyrogallol, resorcinol, catechol, gallic acid and xlenol gave violet spots.

2,4-Dinitrophenol, phenol, quinol and 8-hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline-5-sulphonic acid gave red spots.

Thymol blue, 1,2,5,8-hydroxyanthraquinone and phenyl fluorone, (9-phenyl-2,3,7-trihydroxy-6-fluorone), appeared as grey spots.

1-Nitroso-2-naphthol and bromocresol gave green spots.